

ISOLATING GENOMIC DNA FROM *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES*

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Historic
January 2020: Update into a more complete flowchart. Light modifications about the gel electrophoresis. January 2023: Update about the gel electrophoresis (removal of the BET and use of commercial gels)

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Caution: Trade names or suppliers may be mentioned in the description of the products necessary for applying this method. This information is given as an indication for users of the method and does not constitute an endorsement by the EURL for *Listeria monocytogenes*. Equivalent products may be used if it has been demonstrated that they lead to the same results.

1. EQUIPMENTS

- Thermostated centrifuge (6 000-20 000 rcf)
- 1.5ml microcentrifuge tubes (safelock if possible)
- UV-visible spectrophotometer (600 nm) adapted to the measurement of the turbidity of cell density
- Spectrophotometric cuves (4ml PS or PMMA)
- Spectrophotometer cuvette
- Water or dry bath at 37 °C ± 1°C
- Dry bath 80°C ± 3°C
- Fluorometer (Qubit)
- Micro-volume spectrophotometer (Nanodrop)
- E-gel power snap system (Invitrogen)

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2. CULTURE MEDIA AND REAGENTS

2.1 CULTURE MEDIA

Non-selective solid media adapted for Lm culture: Tryptone Soy Agar with 0.6% of yeast extract (TSAYE).
Non-selective liquid media adapted for Lm culture: Brain heart medium (BHI).

2.2 REAGENTS

- Isopropanol, room temperature (GHS02, GHS07)
- 70% ethanol, room temperature (H225, H319)
- EDTA (50 mM, pH 8.0)
- Water (molecular biology grade)
- 10mg/ml lysozyme (ref 10 837 059 001, Roche)
- Nuclei Lysis Solution (ref A7941, Promega)
- RNase Solution (ref A797C, Promega)
- Protein Precipitation Solution (ref A795A, Promega)
- 0.8% agarose E-gel (ref A25798, ThermoFisher Scientific)
- E-gel 1kb plus DNA ladder (ref 10488090, ThermoFisher Scientific)
- Qubit dsDNA HS Assay Kit (ref Q32854, Invitrogen)

3. OPERATING PROCEDURE: DNA EXTRACTION AND QUALITY CONTROLS

The extraction is performed on confirmed strains of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains according to the method EN ISO 11290-1 and 2.

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Rehydrated DNA

Vortex 30sec
Centrifuge quickly

I. DNA Purity UV Absorbance
Nanodrop

2µl of sample
260 nm / 280 nm ratio : protein contamination
260 nm / 230 nm ratio : organic compounds contamination

Target $1,6 < N < 2,4$

II. Fluorometric quantification
Qubit

Use a 10 fold dilution of extracted DNA
Prepare High sensitivity mix buffer according to manufacturer instructions

The diagram illustrates the Qubit assay workflow. It starts with 'Ensure all reagents are at room temperature'. A bottle of 'iQuant™ Buffer' is shown. A pipette adds '1 x n µL' of 'iQuant™ Reagent' to a tube containing '199 x n µL' of 'iQuant™ Working Solution'. This mixture is then split into two paths: 'Standards from kit' and 'User Samples'. For standards, 10 µL of standard is added to 190 µL of the mixture, resulting in a final volume of 200 µL. For user samples, 1-50 µL of sample is added to 150-199 µL of the mixture, also resulting in a final volume of 200 µL. A note at the bottom states 'n = number of standards + number of samples'.

III. DNA integrity and RNA contamination
Agarose Gel electrophoresis

Take a 0.8% agarose E-gel
Place the e-gel specific size marker: e-gel 1Kb PLUS DNA ladder, 18µL in the well marked "M" (and 10 if not used)
Deposit 20-100ng (maximum 500ng) of DNA into wells 2-10 (plot the amount of DNA deposited in each well) of DNA deposited in each well). A volume of 10µL should be deposited in the wells
Run the e-gel NGS program (26 minute migration) following the "e-gel Power Snap Electrophoresis System"
Take a picture of the gel with the e-gel Power Snap reader, adjust the brightness (+/-) if necessary

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